

Design Guide for Climate Farm Demo Project On-farm Demonstrations

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List of Abbreviations

CFD	Climate Farm Demo
NC	National Coordinator
PDF	Pilot Farm Demo
WP	Work Package
AMM	Adaptation and Mitigation Measure
AMP	Adaptation and Mitigation Plan

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Abstract

One of the most important objectives of the Climate Farm Demo Project is to support the delivery of 4,500 high quality demonstration events in a multi-actor setting across the 1,500 pilot demonstration farmers (PDF's). Demonstration events support farmer-to-farmer learning and are recognised as an important element in an overall advisory service for farmers. Successful demonstration events, during this project, have the potential to increase the uptake and application of climate smart farming approaches and practices by EU farmers.

This design guide should be used as a blueprint for advisors to support the delivery of demonstration events across the 27 partner countries drawing on both outputs from previous EU funded projects, and the experiences of project partner organisations. Potential demonstration approaches (including on-farm and virtual events), the multi-actor approach to farm demos and how best to demonstrate the complexity of the change in farmer behaviour required are discussed in detail throughout.

Finally, simple steps to organise farm demo events are outlined, including defining the objective(s) for the demonstration event, facilitation and learning approaches and evaluating the overall event. The guide offers effective tips along with real life examples of how to successfully plan, deliver and evaluate a farm demo event.

What is a demonstration event¹?

Demonstration farms have a long tradition and have proved to be an effective means of supporting farmers in problem solving at the farm level. Such farms host demonstration events or activities. According to the Oxford Dictionary a demonstration is defined as (a) “The action or process of showing the existence or truth of something by giving proof or evidence”, and (b) “A practical exhibition and explanation of how something works or is performed”. On-farm demonstrations facilitate an effective learning situation for farmers to “see the animals/ crops themselves”, “compare practices in similar situations to their own”, “interact with the scientists and extension workers in the field”, “get doubts clarified themselves” and “jointly solve problems”. “Seeing is believing” and farmer-to-farmer learning underpin on-farm demonstrations.

Demonstration events allow farmers to see a new/innovative technology, practice or system in operation on a working farm not too dissimilar to their own and talk to someone (the demonstration farmer) actively engaged in the practice and to whom they can relate (a peer). Ideally these events are held in-person (to facilitate the exchange of ideas and insights, and to foster farmer-to-farmer learning), but virtual demo events can also be organised (although the facilitation of farmer-to-farmer learning is more challenging), and the demonstration farmer can also share their experiences at locations other than on their own farms e.g. at conferences, trade fairs, large scale farmer events.

Demonstration events (and the demonstration farms upon which they are held) can play a key role in extending climate farm solutions to more farmers, through the provision of practical, tangible experiences of farming methods and technologies that they can subsequently use to improve their own farming practices.

Within the Climate Farm Demo project, an event is considered as a demonstration event if it meets the following criteria:

1. Ideally events for farmers should be held on a Pilot Demonstration Farm (PDF), Lighthouse Farm or Experimental Farm (in other words on one of the farms selected to participate in the project). However, there will be some scope for carrying out demo events in a digital format (scripted videos, Facebook live, story on YouTube or Instagram etc... and/or in a location that

¹ This section relies on content from two published papers, namely,

1. Pappa, E., Koutsouris, A., Ingram, J., Debruyne, L., Cooreman, H. and Marchand, F., (2018). Structural aspects of on-farm demonstrations: key considerations in the planning and design process. *International Journal of Agricultural Extension*, Vol. 6, No. 3, pp. 79 - 90.
2. Ingram, J., Chiswella, H., Mills, J., Debruyne, L., Cooreman, H., Koutsouris, A., Pappa, E. and Marchand, F., (2018). Enabling learning in demonstration farms: a literature review. *International Journal of Agricultural Extension*, Vol. 6, No. 3, pp. 29 - 42.

is not the farmer's farm (at a conference or trade show for example). Guidelines relating to these "alternative" types of demonstration activity will be provided later.

2. A minimum attendance of around 10 farmers (with no maximum number of attendees);
3. An event objective relating to the demonstration of climate smart farming approaches or technologies;
4. Facilitates farmer-to-farmer learning and exchange of ideas;
5. Pre-registered on the project website;
6. Post-evaluated on the project website.

The Climate Farm Demo project will benefit from the Farm Demo toolkits and tutorials developed in the NEFERTITI project - both for running face-to-face demonstration events and in digital or online format (NEFERTITI was funded by H2020 / January 2018 - December 2021). Below are the main links:

Organizing on farm demonstrations

- Link to Farm Demo guidelines: <https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/demo-design-guide> (Available in all EU languages)
- Link to Farm Demo tutorial: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VhnM6C8Nv_M&list=PLOYrtkIDkcdQ54a61JmJ44g8g8_zr4IHPA&index=23 (Subtitles available in 16 EU languages)
- Tools for on farm demonstrations: <https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/> (Available in all EU languages)
- Tutorial for tools: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VA8Vd267jKc>

Organizing virtual demonstrations

- Link to farm demo guidelines: <https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/demo-design-guide-for-virtual-demonstrations/> (Available in all EU languages)
- Link to Farm Demo tutorial: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kwAQuIL20SY> (Subtitles available in 16 EU languages)
- Tools for on farm demonstrations: <https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/> (Available in all EU languages)
- Tutorial for tools: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VA8Vd267jKc>

1. Planning the Demo Event

For any demo event, it is important to explicitly state clear objective(s) and key messages well in advance. They determine all the other decisions you will make during the preparation and the performance of the demo event: the set-up, which actors to involve, and the evaluation of effectiveness. Start by addressing the 'why' (why are we doing this demo) and then the 'what' (what do we want to demonstrate). From these demo objectives subsequently follows the 'who' (the targeted audience for the demo) and the 'how' (the demo set-up and learning methods).

Figure 1 : Four key questions

1.1 Motivating yourself for the event: why organise a demo event?

CFD demonstration events are a central component of the overall project. They will allow the Climate Farm Advisors (CFA's), working with the Pilot Demonstration Farmer (PDF), and other relevant AKIS actors, to demonstrate and promote climate solutions to a wider farming audience. These events will provide an opportunity for the demonstration farmer who has used a specific adaptation and mitigation measure (AMM) or a number of AMM's on their farm to share their experiences and insights while supporting knowledge exchange and co-creation among farmers and other actors. It is expected that CFD demonstration events will:

- Allow climate solutions/ AMM's be demonstrated in situ;
- Provide an opportunity for the farmer to share their experiences;
- Leverage the advisory and support efforts with the demo farmer by reaching more farmers;

- Build trust between CFA, AKIS actors and farmers; and
- Highlight the initial starting point (first event) and progress made on the farm over time (at second and subsequent events);
 - First demo event – present the starting point or baseline, explain how the figures were arrived at, and share the Adaptation and Mitigation Plan (AMP) for the farm;
 - Second demo event – review progress made, focussing on good practices continued and new mitigation practices adopted;
 - Third demo event – again review progress made, present the results of the second audit, compare results with those from the first audit, highlight emissions reduction achieved and explain how the various on-farm changes contributed to the emissions reduction over time. Any benefits accrued by the farmer as a result of rewarding mechanisms/ carbon farming benefits should also be highlighted.

Where possible identify the AMM's used on the farm, and provide the impacts of these practices on GHG emissions (and ammonia emissions and C sequestration, if relevant). Where appropriate, steps taken by the PDF to adapt to climate change should also be highlighted. These impacts (emissions reduction) and changes (adaptation) should be available from the tool used for the audit. Other environmental considerations (biodiversity, water quality) should also be highlighted. The impact of the AMM's on-farm system profitability should also be highlighted.

The overall aim is to accelerate knowledge exchange and capacity building amongst EU farmers to accelerate the uptake of climate smart farming practices. In 2020, Europe committed to being the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. Coupled with this, the "Fit for 55" package, aims to meet the target of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990. Furthermore, the Farm to Fork (F2F) strategy emphasizes the need to accelerate the transition to a sustainable food system and highlights the need to develop new green business models.

Possible targeted effects of your demonstration events could include:

- **Building awareness.** Demos can raise awareness amongst participants regarding climate change (although in some EU countries farmers are already aware of this), climate policy, the social licence to farm or health and safety issues. Also, sustainability topics are often not addressed explicitly but are often part of the demonstration to create awareness with the participants.
- **Problem-solving.** Demos are a useful platform to link advisory/ extension priorities to the needs of local farmers. You can demonstrate solutions to farmers' problems, for example, related to reducing farm labour or how to grow crops in a changing climate, or you can validate conducted research and innovations under local conditions and tailor them to the farmers' needs.
- **Research implementation.** On-farm demo events can act as a platform to transfer knowledge on applied research results to agricultural practice. Innovations and practices can be trialled, compared or validated in 'real' farm conditions.
- **Networking.** Demo events can act as a meeting place for participants. Regular (e.g., yearly) demo events can be used as network events to gather all people involved in the programme, network or project. They can contribute to the strengthening and development of collaboration and boost possible partnerships for cooperative problem solutions, both national and international. Also, the social aspect of networking, being able to meet other farmers, is very attractive to some participants. This could be particularly important if organising events for the PDF's in a country or region.

- **Knowledge co-creation.** You can aim to create (new) knowledge, by profiting from the knowledge pool of the participants that attend the demo event.
- **Innovation adoption.** Demos help the transfer of new opportunities, novelties or practical experience that can be used directly on farms. These innovations can emerge from research, business (related to product sales) or pioneer farmers and such demonstrations can give farmers the confidence to make a grounded decision on the usefulness of the demonstrated practices or innovations for their own farm.
- **Training.** Demos serve as a platform for skills enhancement and capacity building, thus enabling the practical implementation of innovative practices on the farm.
- **Policy implementation.** Demos are an opportunity to inform farmers about new legislation and policy regulations and to provide specific practices and examples of how they can implement them on their farms.

Figure 2 : An advisor addressing farmers at an event (Source: FiBL/Thomas Alföldi)

1.2 Making GHG emissions/ emissions reduction real

Using a farmer's actual performance figures and data should be at the front and centre of any demonstration event. For years, farmers have always benchmarked against each other and it should be no different when it comes to climate change or reducing GHG emissions. Farmers can embrace these changes by learning from one another, in the knowledge that much of what is being asked of them can contribute to improving overall farm profitability, and that there are strong synergies between environmental performance and market dynamics. This is where the emphasis should be placed when

organising on-farm events as farmers will be drawn to the financial benefits quicker than the environmental ones.

Central to making GHG emissions/ emissions reduction real will be the availability of a farm specific figure for GHG emissions. The CFD project will identify a range of GHG measurement/ accounting tools, and it will be the responsibility of the CFA's to select an appropriate tool, to become familiar with its use and the reports generated by it, and to identify the most appropriate figures to highlight at future farm demo events. Training will be provided to CFA's.

1.3 What motivates farmers to attend?

Financial rewards

Naturally farmers will be drawn to monetary values or the demonstration of (mitigation) actions which also increase farm profitability and it is important to highlight this at on-farm events by quantifying monetary gains associated with different actions. For example, farmers across Ireland have embraced the practice of measuring and monitoring grass growth on their farms as it is the cheapest form of feed available to them.

In addition to the cost savings which can benefit the farmer due to the adoption of a specific AMM e.g. reducing fertiliser use can save the farmer money, there may also be a benefit to the farmer through future rewarding mechanisms currently being developed by the EU e.g. increasing the rate of soil carbon sequestration can lead to increased carbon in the soil which will have a value. Details of rewarding mechanisms, and the steps to availing of them, will be provided by WP6. This topic could be an interesting one for demonstration events in the later years of the project, particularly if the PDF has availed of such mechanisms, and is prepared to share their experiences.

Perceived responsibilities

Farmers might be motivated to attend an event due to personal valuation of biodiversity and the environment which can, combined with problem awareness, lead to feelings of responsibility. Increasing the environmental values of farmers can be triggered through communication at CFD events amongst farmers as well as between farmers and other stakeholders, and feedback loops that could spark enthusiasm for conservation.

Social norms

Farmers might be more motivated to participate in on-farm demo events if they feel it is appreciated by the social group they identify with, which is in most cases a formal or informal network of peer farmers. Hence, it can be important to enhance group norms that build toward a collective goal (reducing GHG emissions) and that emphasize duty.

Descriptive norms

Apart from existing or evolving group norms of duty to engage in reducing GHG emissions, farmers might also be motivated through others' actual engagement, e.g., neighbouring farmers acting as social role models. The peer pressure a farmer perceives can, however, encourage or hinder participation, depending on the local context. The desire for social approval, respect, and a good reputation can motivate individual farmers to behave like the peers they perceive as 'good' farmers. Maintaining their

own reputation is another attribute referring to the concept of social capital and related to trust and reciprocity. For example, in Ireland, farmers might wish to fit in with their local discussion group or take on a group project with farmers in their locality.

Ultimately, farmers should want to attend the event for their own reason be it financial or social. If a farmer attends an event and isn't interested in the discussion or learning outcomes, he/she won't take any messages home with them. The responsibility lies with the advisors to ensure the events are kept relevant, informative and fresh. So, being aware of issues of concern to farmers are framing demo events around these "current topics" can be helpful in making the demo event more attractive to potential attendees.

1.4 Who should attend your farm demo event?

Over the lifespan of the project, it is hoped that 150,000 EU farmers will have attended one of the planned 4,500 on-farm demonstration events. These farmers will come from different backgrounds running different systems; intensive/extensive, conventional/organic systems across livestock, tillage and horticulture enterprises. The target groups should be tailored in relation to:

- Farming enterprise (dairy/beef/sheep/tillage)
- Region (nationwide, specific province, international)
- Early adopters/innovators versus late adopters/ laggards (organisers could tailor an event to suit more open-minded farmers or experts in a certain area, and organise separate events for less engaged farmers).
- System e.g., intensive vs extensive.

Open vs. Closed demo events

An "open" demo event is one where a general invitation is extended to a wide audience, with no restrictions on attendance. A "closed" demo event is one where participation is by direct invitation only.

To increase the trust and tighten the network and sharing of details amongst demo farmers closed demo events could be held whereby the events are targeted solely for demo farmers (participating in the project). Holding these events will create friendships and bonds allowing farmers an informal setting to thrash out their views and answer any questions they may have. Lighthouse farms and experimental farms provide the ideal location for such events.

Ideally the majority of events on the PDF's would be organised as "open" type events.

Farming enterprise

Events should always be open to the general public irrespective of the enterprise on the host farm but it makes sense to keep the events tailored to specific enterprises. For example, dairy farmers are going to relate more to the key messages being addressed on a dairy farm. From an advisor's point of view, it is also easier to sell messages to the same cohort of farmers when carrying out simple exercises or encouraging interaction from the attendees.

Region

Geographic location also plays an important role when targeting farmers. Different locations experience different challenges e.g., land type, weather, terrain etc... For example, speaking about turning livestock outdoors in one region might be 6-8 weeks before another if the land type is free draining or heavy soils.

It must also be noted farmers aren't going to travel long distances to attend a particular event so this will influence the promotion of events and whom you are targeting to attend.

Early Adopters/Laggards (farmer mindset)

Some farmers are information hungry and always on the lookout for the latest research and advice whereas others are more sceptical to adopting new farming techniques. For example, in Ireland the discussion group model has worked well where farmers are placed in groups according to their system, region and mind-set and the same thinking could be used when organising farm events depending on the messages being conveyed.

System

Again, when organising an event, it should be kept as streamlined as possible. For example, in Ireland, if there was a tillage event it would be targeted at specific crop growers e.g., spring barley as opposed to winter wheat.

It must be noted CFA's should liaise with local advisors when targeting farmers to attend an event in a particular region. Local knowledge can provide key insights into what has happened on the ground recently. This information is invaluable and something that must not be overlooked when preparing for an event. Similarly, stakeholders may have a feel for a particular area from dealing with farmers on a regular basis and should be involved when targeting farmers to attend events. For example, some areas in Ireland often experience a summer drought. Relaying messages on how to minimise the effect of the drought would be topical at some farm events but in other parts of the country it would not carry any relevance.

1.5 Who should you involve in planning the event?

The farmer hosting the event should be front and centre when organising the event, and should be part of the organising group. Relevant stakeholders should be invited to participate at the planning stage in a multi-actor approach. No CFA should undertake organising a demo event by him/herself and should instead focus on building a strong team around them.

1.6 What do you want to demonstrate?

Ultimately the programme wants to demonstrate the positive journey the demo farmers are undertaking and how they are going to reduce their GHG emissions by 35% along the project life, thus achieving the EU 2030 Climate Target Plan.

The demo events will highlight the uptake and use of climate smart farming solutions across the EU. The application and use of both adaptation (system change) and mitigation measures should be demonstrated, with a particular focus on adaptation measures that also bring mitigation benefits (where appropriate).

This protocol for demonstration events is produced based on 'Farm Demo' experiences and focuses on what the PDF has encountered along his/her journey.

A learning approach: Within the overall project, the organisation and delivery of demo events will be monitored and evaluated on an annual basis. Lessons learned will be capitalised to improve CFD demo event's quality and to produce both recommendations and guidelines for training.

Demonstration topics can vary from one event to the next, or an overall theme may be chosen for a series of events. For example, the demonstration of a product, a machine, a process, management or marketing but ultimately it should all be centred around the farmer and what has happened on the ground (the aim should be to demonstrate the AMM's implemented by the farmer on their farm, and on the impact of these changes on farm performance, including GHG emissions).

Every country will have different resources at their disposal for the delivery of on-farm demo events. For example, Teagasc has a large network of agricultural advisors whom work together across the country thus messages are easily disseminated and it is easier to plan and deliver a farm event with more help on the ground. This is not the case in all EU countries. All advisors should build on existing on-going national and regional dynamics, expertise, actions and projects. CFD should be used to accelerate these dynamics and their impact. It must also be recognised CFD activities must be connected and grounded within local activities and not isolated.

The characteristics of the topic demonstrated influence the demo set-up and which target groups can potentially be reached. Is it an innovation not at all known by the farming community with no real-life implementation examples? Is it already implemented by a minority of farmers? Is it a widespread practice that could be optimised and refined by farmers? Often the strength of a demo event lies in its simplicity. It is therefore advisable to limit the number of topics addressed during one event.

If you want to address multiple topics, you may consider organising a series of demo events or making sure sufficient time is planned for each individual topic.

The choice of the topic can be made top-down by the organisers, by farmer representatives, or by the project in which the demo is embedded, as well as bottom-up with farmer involvement, or by participants in a previous demo event when it involves a series of demo events. Furthermore, the annual Knowledge Exchange Plan (WP1) or the Annual Dynamic Action Plan for Demo Events (WP3) should inform the themes for individual demo events (or series of events), and support the bottom-up selection of relevant topics. Either way, a thorough consideration or discussion beforehand is necessary to select an interesting, inspiring and relevant topic.

1.7 What to avoid when planning on-farm events?

- Don't procrastinate - you can never start planning your event too early.
- Don't be afraid to ask for help from colleagues or other advisors within your organisation or involved in the project,
- Don't be afraid to delegate and share responsibilities.
- Don't forget to engage with the host farmer before, during and after the event.
- Don't put all your eggs in one basket and prepare for the worst e.g. if weather is bad.
- Practice makes perfect; don't presume everyone knows their role – it is best practice to schedule a “dry run”.

Example of tools for on-farm demonstrations are available at the following link:
<https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/>

Tutorial for tools: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VA8Vd267jKc>

1.8 Date and time of the event

Particular consideration should be given when setting the date and time of the event, with a view to maximising attendance. For example, holding an event targeted towards dairy farmers should be planned between milking times e.g. avoiding early morning and evening to facilitate milking times on farm. Consideration should also be given to farmers who are working part time or focusing on an event for female farmers. Early spring time is often a very busy period on farms so working with farmers to ensure they are happy to host an event is paramount. Simple things like ensuring no other event in the same locality is on the same day will all have a positive effect on the attendance.

1.9 Virtual farm demo events

The project preference is for in-person demo events held on the PDF's. This is because one of the reasons for the success of demonstration events is the opportunity provided for other farmers to see, touch, smell and experience the technology on a real farm. This can be hard to replicate during a virtual demo event. That said, the project will consider virtual demo events. Specific guidelines will be issued, but as a starting point, the following criteria need to be met:

- The host farmer should have a prominent role in the virtual event;
- Participant engagement should be planned, and should go further than asking participants to “submit questions via the Chat function”;

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- Consideration should be given to virtual break-out rooms to facilitate farmer-to-farmer discussion;
- Images or videos from the “host farm” (while the demonstration is being delivered virtually, a PDF should still be identified as the host) should be created and used to illustrate the discussion.

Guidelines on virtual demonstration events are available at this link:
<https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/demo-design-guide-for-virtual-demonstrations/>

2. Making the Best Use of the Host Farmer

The focus of this section is on working with the demo farmer to ensure that they are fully involved in both the planning and delivery of the demo event. CFA's should consider each of the following questions in relation to the host farmer and their farm when planning and preparing for a demo event.

- How can best use be made of the host farmer experiences?
- How can you create opportunities for audience involvement?
- Is the host farmer an experienced public speaker?
- Can farmers relate with the host farmer and their farm?
- Is the host farm suitable for the demo event, taking into account the topic, the location and the planned activities?
- Where should the PDF stand on climate adaptation and mitigation?

2.1 How can best use be made of the host farmer experiences?

The host farmer needs to be central to the discussion on the farm. Ideally, appoint a facilitator to ask questions of the host farmer. Have these questions pre-prepared with the host farmer. In discussion with the host farmer consider the success of adopting particular climate solutions that have worked well for him/her over the last number of years, problems and solutions encountered on the farm, along with the positive and negative side effects of technology.

For example, take a farmer who has started using a different fertiliser product, protected urea, on his/her farm. Talk through the mitigation action with him or her following a series of questions:

1. Where did they first come across the action?
2. Did they do any research on the product before using it on their farm?
3. Has it changed the way they previously farmed?
4. What is the main advantage or disadvantage of using the product?
5. What is the cost benefit?
6. What would you say to someone who has never used the product?

2.2 How can you create opportunities for audience involvement?

The success of a farm walk can be greatly improved by actively giving participants the opportunity to (1) ask questions of the host farmer and (2) share their experiences with the audience. This might involve: allocating adequate time for a “Q&A session” with the host farmer, organising discussions with smaller numbers of participants, organising group exercises with small groups or creating opportunities for more informal knowledge exchange, e.g., over a cup of tea.

Figure 3: Audience involvement at an event (Source: FiBL/Thomas Alföldi)

2.3 Is the host farmer an experienced public speaker?

All the academic literature suggests ‘other farmers’ are farmers’ most frequently reported source of information. While it does not make a difference if a farmer is an extrovert or an introvert when it comes to hosting an event on farm it is extremely important to know how comfortable he/she is with public speaking in order to relay on-farm messages. Whilst it makes the job of the advisor a lot easier if the farmer in question can handle the pressure of speaking in front of an audience it is not a necessity as it is your job as the facilitator to probe and extract the information, relaying the messages through the farmer in question.

2.4 Can farmers relate with the host farmer and their farm?

A demo event might have more impact when the host farm operates under the same ‘real life’ conditions as average farms e.g., soil type, scale of operation, level of capital investment etc.. On the other hand, for example, pioneer farmers can show innovative and more experimental techniques. This is an important consideration in the current project for CFA’s as they are selecting the PDF’s, as the farmers selected during 2023, will be expected to host CFD demo events for the remainder of the project duration. Advisers should use their own, or others, local knowledge to identify farmers who have the following characteristics:

- Somebody other farmers check with about a new technology or farming approach
- An opinion leader
- Respected
- Already central to local networks
- A history of embracing change

Figure 4: Interaction at an event (Source: FiBL/Thomas Alföldi)

The public perception of the host also plays a role in the attractiveness of the event to the potential participants. Choosing someone you already know or a farm that is appointed by organisations for several years, during which trials are tested on the farm, can be a ‘safe’ option as the demo events often require a lot of effort from the hosts to prepare their farm for the visitors. On the opposite side using the same farmer can become repetitive (unless of course the advisor can “freshen up” the event over time) and the event can lose some of its appeal.

Note: Time and careful consideration must be given at the selection process, as once the farmers are selected, they must host three events as participants of the CFD project.

2.5 Is the host farm suitable for the demo event, taking into account the topic, the location and the planned activities?

The host farmer's activities, practices and farm facilities should be aligned or coincide with the purpose of the demo and the expected number of participants.

Ideally, there should be a wide geographic distribution of demo farms so that farmers can benchmark themselves to someone in a similar region. Equally, it is important that the PDF is not isolated or in an isolated area e.g. the only tillage farmer in a predominantly grassland area. Travel time is often a deciding factor upon deciding to attend an event or not. However certain participants (innovators and early adopters) are willing to travel further for demos on innovative techniques that are not common in their own region.

2.6 Where should the PDF stand on climate adaptation and mitigation?

Ultimately, it is hoped the Pilot Demo Farmers (PDF's) will act as case studies subsequently improving the understanding and encouraging discussion on the potential impact of climate change on the sector, and the impact of the adoption of AMM's on mitigating the effects of climate change. With 1,500 farmers involved it will make it easier for other farmers to benchmark themselves against these farms and also to learn from them.

Ideally, the PDF should work with their CFA to agree an AMP, and subsequently to implement the agreed adaptation and mitigation actions. It is the demonstration of these measures, and the sharing of the PDF's experiences, which should form the centre point of the demo event. If the PDF is a "climate denier" or even somewhat sceptical about the need for climate action, then it is likely that they will not make a suitable PDF, and the demo event will struggle to meet the objectives of the project.

That said, there could be lessons learnt if a willing PDF struggles to implement a climate solution, or even their rejection of a solution as unsuitable; that suggests that the AMM is not ready for adoption in its current state, or perhaps needs to be tailored for the locality or particular farm.

3. Farm Demo Setup

Having identified the objectives for your demo event, and established an organising group, consulted with the host farmer and other stakeholders the next step for the advisor is to consider the various practical steps required to deliver the demo event. This chapter will provide guidelines for registration and reporting about face-to-face demonstration events within the course of the Climate Farm Demo Project.

This section (or chapter) should be perceived as a guideline for the process of registering and implementing practical steps for setting up an on-farm demo event.

The guidelines protocol on how to register a demo event on the project website is available in the CFD Website User Guide document, while this document includes relevant links to the project website which can be found here [Climate Farm Demo](#). Herewith, you may also find other tools that may help you within the process e.g., a draft invitation letter, as well as a registration form and evaluation form.

3.1 Ten steps to organising a Climate Farm Demo demonstration event

1. *Identify your focus-* define why you are organising the event
2. *Build your team-* it's impossible to cover all the aspects of the farm event by yourself
3. *Consider your target audience-* In the lead up to the event you should anticipate who will be audience
4. *Select/discuss topics with your host farmer-* Ideally the topic is something the farmer has excelled at and will stand out on the day of the event
5. *Register the event on the project website.* climatefarmdemo.eu
6. *Define your content-* Discuss with the farmer. Use research findings to reinforce on farm situations/experiences
7. *Complete a Health and Safety Check-* Walk the farm prior to the event and complete a checklist. An example of a health and safety checklist is provided in the appendices
8. *Ensure you have informative boards-* focus on 2-3 learning outcomes/key messages (see images below)
9. *Advertise your event-* Local papers/radio, messages to existing clients or farmers in the locality. Example of a colourful flier below promoting an event
10. *Share the GPS location for the event and ensure that different routes to the event and appropriately signposted*
11. *Complete your final checks-* sound check (to ensure all mics/speakers are working), all boards correct and in place. Guest speakers know where their stand is located. Complete a practice/dry run of the event
12. *Plan your event for audience interaction-* identify opportunities to break the groups into small numbers to make farmers more comfortable

3.2 Multi-Actor Approach

- Farm advisors can act as potential ‘multipliers’ of the key messages of the demo. They can spread and increase the demo content to non-participating farmers and they can connect farmers who applied a practice or innovation to those who are interested. Again, on a local level advisors will know what events were previously held in the area. In general advisors may specialise in certain areas for example a dairy advisor or a tillage advisor. Both will bring different attributes and insights into organising an event. Having more advisors around at the pre-planning stage should not be underestimated.
- Actors from the agri-food chain (e.g. suppliers, food processors, consumers...) are important partners in cooperative solutions and their presence can strengthen the links between producers and markets. They can contribute with data and experience from other areas. Dealing with farmers on a weekly basis they will also have local knowledge of what is happening on the ground which can feed into targeting farmers and also choosing topics for the event. Collaboration gives the possibility to share ideas and turn existing knowledge and research results into innovative solutions that can more easily be put into practice. The interaction and co-creation among actors are key elements for a trans-disciplinary approach that have the potential to address future challenges such as the reduction of GHG emissions.
- Collaboration with commercial partners can realise very effective demo events in terms of knowledge and information provision. However, sound agreements with commercial companies, prior to the demo event, are needed to avoid farmers perceiving the event as a sales pitch. This can be avoided by involving more than one commercial company present or inviting “neutral” parties like non-commercial advisory services or researchers alongside the commercial company. The success of a demo is often also related to how the organising team is perceived by the local community. Organising teams can therefore benefit from collaboration with respected local organisations that have a lot of contact with farmers.
- Policy makers can raise awareness of policy barriers and incentives which might increase the anchoring and scaling of the demo content on one hand, but also learn themselves on the practical problems or barriers farmers are confronted with to improve policy regulation. On the other hand, farmers are often reluctant to participate and share experiences in a group when there are policy makers present in the group.
- (Agricultural) students and teachers can bring in research innovations, they can question the farmers on their ways of producing while learning about farming practices. They can help to carry out monitoring & evaluation, learn from co-organising and are good extra hands.
- Media and communications personnel can provide insights relating to event promotion and the framing of key messages (but many advisers can have skills in these areas also).

Figure 5: An advisor speaking at an event (Source: Author's own image)

Selecting Cows for Dairy AI

- Not all about the Bull!
- Increasing Selection Pressure within Breeding Females will Maximise Genetic Gain!

Animal Group	Num of Cows	Milk Kg	Fat %	Prot %	Surv% D/ Days	Milk	Fertility	Carbon	Calv	Beef	Maint	Mgmt	Health	EBI €
Cows with EBI	121	41	9.9	9.15	3.1	€ 64	€ 109	€ 15	€ 46	€ -17	€ 19	€ 2	€ 4	€ 241
Missing EBI	0													
Total Cows	121	8.1	8.12		-5.8									

	Herd Average	Expected %	After Selection	Expected %
Protein	0.12	3.82	0.17	4.01
Fat	0.15	4.55	0.24	4.91
EBI	241		285	

Breed from the best, beef for the rest!

- Average of the best = €88 more profit/lactation

Figure 6: An example of an informative board (Source: Author's own image)

Sexed Semen & Syncing

Sexed Semen		Synchronisation												
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increases ability to breed higher potential replacements but not without risk Target use at most fertile animals <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heifers (Cycling and BCS 3+) Parity 1-4 Cows (>50 DIM, Cycling) NO health issues Follow procedures for maximum success Serve 14-20 hours after heat onset 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fixed Time AI allows for greater control Overcome timing of AI with Sexed Semen Mitigates against potential reduced Conception Rates with Sexed Facilitates more compact calving (facilities!!) Heifers born early – easier group to manage 												
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Onset of heat</th> <th>Time of AI</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>13:00</td> <td>19:00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>16:00</td> <td>22:00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>19:00</td> <td>01:00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>22:00</td> <td>04:00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>01:00</td> <td>07:00</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Onset of heat	Time of AI	13:00	19:00	16:00	22:00	19:00	01:00	22:00	04:00	01:00	07:00	<p style="text-align: center;">For Maximum Success - stick rigidly to the protocol you are using!</p>
Onset of heat	Time of AI													
13:00	19:00													
16:00	22:00													
19:00	01:00													
22:00	04:00													
01:00	07:00													

Figure 7: An example of a board focusing on only two learning outcomes (Source: Author's own image)

Figure 8 provides an example of an advertisement for a demo event. It contains:

- The title of the event – “Beef Challenge”
- Farmer details
- Date and time
- Location (including address code)
- Actors involved in the event
- An attractive image (of stock from the host farm)

Teagasc/IFJ BETTER Farm Beef Challenge Event

Thursday, 4th July
Walks at 2pm & 5pm

**Wesley Browne, Leagh,
Dunraymond, Co. Monaghan**
Eircode: H18 R921

This is a DAFM approved Knowledge Transfer Beef Event

A TEAGASC/IRISH FARMERS JOURNAL INITIATIVE IN ASSOCIATION WITH

Logos: abp, DAWN MEATS, FBD, KEPAK

Figure 8: A colourful and catchy flyer advertising an event (Source: Author's own image)

3.3 Must-do’s at farm events:

- A welcome introduction, ideally introduce the host farmer and let him/her welcome everyone
- Practical demonstration(s) - you are on a farm after all make use of it!
- Allow time for questions after each topic or at a particular board.
- Allow time for farmers to reflect on the key messages and how changes may be implemented on their own farms (typically towards the end of the event, see section 6).
- Ask the participants what they already know to encourage interaction and get the ball rolling
- Focus on delivering two or three clear messages
- Close the event formally and draw clear conclusions/ take-home messages
- Provide a feedback, or evaluation, form to gather participant feedback, so as to improve future demo events. Improvements.

3.4 Pre-event registration

All CFD events must be registered on the project website in advance of the event. Link project website- [ClimateFarmDemo](#)

The information needed for registering for the event is clearly outlined in the appendix titled The Pre-Event Registration Template. **Note, unless the event is registered online prior to the event it will not be recognised as an event within the project.**

3.5 Structure of the farm walk

Include a description of each stand/stop (where information boards are located) at the event including title of the stand, time, persons responsible and location of the stand. Don’t forget to allocate time for questions!

Identify the demonstrations / opportunities for engagement e.g.: farmers may be asked to fill out key information on a board or asked to physically assess something on the farm (grass plot or animals on display)

	Demonstration / Exercise 1
Brief Description	
Staff Responsible/ Required	
Machinery / animals / props required	

Pre planning the route is important as all parties involved know their place prior to the event. It takes out any confusion and speakers can feel more comfortable in their surroundings especially if they are referencing props beside boards. The first stop and the last stop are crucial as it sets the tone for the event with the final stop summarising key take home messages. Introductions are important and consideration needs to be given to who will facilitate time for questions and answers at each stop. Events should flow swiftly but there needs to be a lead taken by a facilitator to provide direction and ensuring time is allocated correctly.

3.6 Use of boards / handouts

Avoid overuse of complicated boards with a lot of information on them. Examples of boards which didn't work well as opposed to good boards are included below.

The board below needs some work as it contains;

- Too much text
- No images

Figure 9: An example of a board with too much text (Source: Author's own image)

On the other hand, the board below works better as it contains;

- Very little text
- Images and visuals
- Take home message

Figure 10: An example of a practical board (Source: Author's own image)

Make best use of the props on the farm, rather than relying on boards and handouts. Props used at farm events can vary depending on the message being delivered. For example, if you were trying to deliver a message around breeding you might have livestock close by to reinforce your point or if it was soil fertility you might have a bag of lime. Below is an image from a breeding event in Ireland.

Figure 11: Stock on show to provide context when speaking about breeding (Source: Author's own image)

A bale of silage alongside meal being used as a prop to emphasise the importance of making quality silage to reduce feed costs

Figure 12: An example of practical props (Source: authors own image)

Don't get too hung up on props either, something as simple as a score card to judge the clover content in a grass/clover sward can often draw in your audience when delivering demo on farm.

Figure 13: : Clover score card (Source: authors own image)

Performing simple interactive exercises on farm with smaller groups of farmers can often bring about greater change as it's often easier to sell messages or promote messages. For example, the image below shows a simple game of Jenga where farmers pick blocks with different initiatives engraved on the blocks and place them according to their significance in reducing GHG emissions.

Figure 14: Jenga with Mitigation Actions (Source: Author's own image)

Having physical products on hand to circulate where farmers can see them in person adds value to the messages being conveyed.

Figure 15: Clover seed and protected urea (Source: Author's own image)

Keep handouts short and to the point. It is important that key results from GHG farm audit are included as KPIs on boards and handouts.

Programme Requirement Ensure all boards / handouts are properly branded.	CFD Corporate Identity Manual (available on SharePoint at this link: CFD - Corporate Identity Manual.pdf)
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3.7 CFD Farm Information Sheet

All advisors will have a lot of work on their hands between conducting the audits and monitoring progress across PDF's. A Farm Information template has been developed which can be used at the beginning of the recruitment process to gather some general information which can be used to give a background to the farm. The document can be updated throughout the course of the project to review progress at different stages. Please refer to the appendix to view the document.

4. Promotion of Events

The promotion of an event should never be underestimated. Ultimately you need events to be well attended in order for messages to spread to the wider farming community. You must plan your promotional activities prior to and on the day of the event to obtain sufficient media exposure.

4.1 When should events be promoted?

Events should be promoted at least 3-4 weeks in advance of the event date.

4.2 How should events be promoted?

Events should be promoted locally e.g., shops, local newspaper etc. Don't rely solely on social media to promote an event as some farmers aren't using social media. Local co-ops/merchants/hardware's should be targeted to attract greater attendances as farmers tend to go these outlets on a weekly basis.

Social media such as Twitter, Facebook and Instagram are popular social media platforms where adverts and promotional fliers can be posted with interaction tracked and accounted for. It is important to have a visual to accompany text in order to attract the farmer's attention along with a catchy slogan or theme for the event. Below is an advert Teagasc posted on Facebook advertising Moorepark'23.

Figure 16: An advert for an event on Facebook (Source: Author's own image)

Again, a multi-actor approach should be taken towards promoting an event as all parties have a role to play to ensure the event is well attended. The advisor should take the lead role and use their networks to get messages out to the wider public but the host has a role to play too. An invitation from the host farmer can go a long way as personal invites are often taken more seriously and can improve attendances at events. He/she should also be encouraged to promote the event through word of mouth.

Stakeholders offer a completely different network to advisors and farmers and again provide another good channel to promoting an event. It's important stakeholders help when it comes to promoting the event as their networks spread into the wider agricultural industry.

4.3 Pre event must do's

Multiple communication channels can be used for recruitment of participants from flyers to text messages to word of mouth. For example, Teagasc have an extremely large client list nationwide servicing thousands of farmers. Where there is an event in a particular region suited to a specific cohort of farmers a short text message would always be sent out a week prior to the event and again 48 hours in advance. Whatever means of communication the message should be centred on the following:

- **Host farmer:** He/she should be front and centre as they are opening their farm gate to host the event to the wider public.
- **Presenter Information:** Share the presenters' names to generate excitement among attendees and keep everyone informed.

- **Event Schedule:** Provide a detailed timeline of the event's activities and presentations so that attendees can plan accordingly.
- **Communication Channel:** Clearly define communication methods for the in-person event and utilize digital tools (social channels) and mobile apps.
- **Food and Beverage Arrangements:** If food and drink are available, communicate this information to attendees as it may increase attendance.

4.4 Going the extra yard to promote an event

Don't put all your eggs in the one basket when it comes to promoting an event. For example don't rely solely on social media platforms to convey certain messages particularly when it comes to promoting an event. Uploading or posting a short video clip on a relevant social media channel is an ideal way to interact with the expected participants.

- Extra information on the host farm, demo content, field trials, specific features to be highlighted at the event
- Ask participants to register online
- Stimulate participants by asking them some reflective questions they can relate to their own farms

In some cases, certain things may be incentivised to attract a greater number of attendees.

- Test samples
- Free soil analysis
- Free forage analysis
- Food and drinks
- Prizes
- Researcher or technical expert as a guest speaker/ to answer farmers' questions

4.5 Signage

Ensuring the location of the event is easily found is a necessity. Too often events are held in a remote location and badly signposted. A precise location should be given . For example in Ireland Eircodes work well as it can bring you to a precise location in other countries it may be a GPS location or a pin.

Figure 17: signage for an event (Source: Author's own image)

4.6 How can we attract farmers/ other participants to attend a demo event related to climate action?

Climate change is perhaps the greatest environmental challenge facing the world right now. All farmers need to be shown that the benefits of adaptation and mitigation methods outweigh the costs. Often it requires a spark of genius or thinking out of the box to come up with “the hook”. All advisors need to constantly relay how important it is to reduce GHG emissions by following four simple points outlined below:

1. The impact of Climate Change

Very often when farmers think of climate change more often than not they don't think it has an impact on their day to day lives. But the impact of climate change across Europe will be felt by all, if climate smart solutions aren't adopted. Table 1 below outlines the potential impacts on how we will farm in the future.

Impact	Risk
Wetter winters	More intense storms and rainfall, increased likelihood and magnitude of river and coastal flooding
Drier summers	Water shortages in summer, heat stress for animals
More frequent extreme weather events	Such as storms and droughts. Risk of fodder shortages, risk of damage to infrastructure
Increased risk of new pests and diseases of animals and plants	This may make it impractical to grow certain crops because of an increase some diseases and parasites

Table 1: The Impact of Climate Change on Weather and the Risk to Agriculture

2. Potential Cost Savings and Enhanced Profits

Many of the actions that farmers are being asked to implement to reduce gaseous emissions can also result in cost savings i.e. a win-win situation, with benefits for the environment and the farmer's pocket. Amongst other actions, improving breeding strategies, improved grazing management, more days at grass, improved animal health, incorporating clover as well as addressing low soil pH all contribute to reducing gaseous emissions as well as reducing input costs and improving profitability.

Finally, European farmers have a long track record of adapting to change and there is no doubt the Climate Farm Demo project will have a positive impact on reducing our emissions.

It is very easy to overlook a simple task in the lead up to an event so every effort should be made to ensure no stone is left unturned. Again, there is a template which all advisors should complete as it outlines a simple step by step guide to promoting an event. The template is located in the Appendix of this guide.

3. Social responsibility

Farmers have a responsibility to their families, future generations of farmers, local communities as well as wider society to minimise the impact on the environment. Farmers take great pride in how the environment they live and farm in looks. While much work has been done and continues to be done, more needs to be done to reduce the overall gaseous emissions.

4. Policy will force change

Across Europe, countries are legally bound by many international agreements, EU policy as well as national policy in the area of climate action. These include the Paris Agreement, the Farm to Fork Strategy, at the heart of the European Green Deal as well as the National Climate Action Bill. These policies, future regulations and incentives will all impact on how farming takes place across Europe in the near future.

5. Learning and Facilitation Methods

An effective demonstrator can be defined as someone who is recognised by the participants as knowledgeable, honest and dedicated; demonstrators should also ideally have experience in facilitation and if not should team up with a colleague who has. Even at demonstration events there may be a need to facilitate dialogue where different attending participants can share their views and opinions. Demonstrations tend to follow a more traditional linear approach where social interaction is often limited to one-way direction from the demonstrator to the participants or at best two-way social interaction whereby the demonstrator may be answering a question from the crowd.

It is easy get bogged down on having the perfect boards or props but if three basic needs- autonomy, relatedness and competence are fulfilled by the demo event, participants will be more likely to actively join in discussions meaning they value the practices and consequently might change their behaviour to align with the practices being discussed. For example, the requirement for autonomy could be met by allowing participants to choose the mitigation actions they would implement on their farms to reduce GHG emissions. While the requirement for relatedness can be met through ensuring that farmers feel comfortable, respected and connected with one another talking about the various AMM's and more specifically, sharing their experiences with a particular AMM on their farm. In relation to competency farmers need to leave the event having learnt different skills or feel confident they can implement particular positive actions on their own farm. This is key to peer-to-peer learning at demonstration events.

5.1. How the facilitator is perceived by the participants

It is not just what an advisor says at an event that will make an impression or will be recalled later on. As important as what is said is how it is said, specifically the body language, gestures and facial expressions of the adviser.

It is important to open the event on the front foot ensuring a positive start to the event! It is not only with words and sounds that people communicate. Messages are sent and received through channels other than speech and hearing. Body language is a very important form (if not the most important) of non-verbal communication. Every facilitator must learn how to use it, but also how to see and interpret it. Some people are very expressive in terms of their body language whilst others are not at all. Some body language can be of a negative nature e.g. folded arms whilst other forms are of a positive nature such as, eye contact. Two of the more common types of body language are gestures and facial expressions.

1. Gestures

There are many forms of gesture which can be used in a positive or negative manner. Generally, a facilitator should be using gestures in a positive manner. The most obvious hand gesture for a facilitator to use is an open handed gesture (palm/palms open) which invites openness or a questioning pose. Equally nodding of the head encourages contribution.

2. Facial Expression

This form of body language can either have a positive or negative effect, depending on the expression used. It can be definitive or questioning. Physical Position within the Group As a facilitator, it is important that you are very aware of this. Generally, it is important that you take a central or prominent position in the group. Groups should be in small numbers at events and operate largely in a U-shape or circular or semi-circular shaped structure. This creates an open environment, but also allows prominence of the facilitator/speaker. There are situations however that you, as the facilitator, should step back to the periphery. An example of this is when discussion is coming from the crowd.

TOP TIP: 'Don't rely on the Board!' Use experiences from host farm and take any lead that may come from the crowd in the form of questions.

5.2 Group size and composition

The decision on the group size depends on the objective(s) of the demo and has a major impact on the format of your demo event.

- Smaller groups (8-15 participants):
 - More effective for knowledge exchange, reflection and deeper peer-to-peer learning.
 - Easier to manage.
 - Small closed groups who meet regularly have built up trust, possibly enabling even more effective discussions.
- Larger groups:
 - When the objective is to raise awareness and wide knowledge transfer.
 - Help to attract sponsors and farm supplying companies.
 - Need good audio systems and visuals
 - If planned for, larger groups can be sub-divided into smaller groups for discussion

More homogeneous groups appear to be 'prepared to share' and to trust other participants, while groups made up of different types of actors can be beneficial to spark discussions and networking, by looking at the same problem together from different angles. This is of course also an important element when thinking about encouraging farmers to attend events.

Also, the extent of familiarity between the participants can have a big impact on the group dynamics, and can influence the appropriateness of some learning methods over others. This is particularly evident if a discussion group attends an event together. You need more organised facilitation methods to spark networking, sharing and discussions for groups that don't know each other. A skilful and friendly facilitator can create a nice and friendly atmosphere and environment that makes it easier for farmers to speak openly and create a good discussion.

5.3 Involving the host farmer

Effective hosts use their personality and facilitation skills in a way that helps the demonstration farmer (PDF) talk about what is important to them, share their insights regarding a particular technology, integrate other actors – for example, researchers and technical experts – into the conversations, while at the same time, making the event attractive and memorable for the attendees.

If the facilitator is effective, the attendees will build a strong and positive emotional relationship with the demonstration farmer.

How can effective hosting help me serve event attendees?

- I can help the farmers feel optimistic about their work and the adoption of new technologies;
- I can help farmers find their voice, to ask questions and to seek clarifications; and
- I can help farmers move from talk to action.

How can being an effective host help me produce better on farm events?

- It teaches me to listen as well as to speak;.
- It emphasizes the need for me to communicate clearly;.
- It confirms that I must plan my events at least six weeks in advance; and it helps me make interesting and memorable events.

5.4 Twelve key facilitation tasks

1. Respect the host farmer, involving them throughout at all stages.
2. Understand and respect your farmer-listeners.
3. Earn your attendees trust and respect.
4. Communicate clearly.
5. Convey realistic optimism.
6. Help farmers ask questions and seek answers.
7. Plan your boards and speakers
8. Be a good listener.
9. Be prepared, practice your presentation and overall approach beforehand, complete a “dry run”
10. Promote the move from talk to action.
11. Make your event interesting and memorable.
12. Improve your performance over time through feedback.

5.5 Selection of suitable learning methods

There are three basic principles:

1. Relate learning content to farming practice
2. Engage participants in active knowledge exchange
3. Use a variety of learning methods

5.5.1 | Relate learning content to farming practice

Pay attention to the broader context. Address the impact of the demonstrated practice or innovation on the whole farm, and also discuss the wider context (e.g. societal, economic, and political). By providing this additional information participants can make more informed decisions on whether or not to adopt a practice or innovation. Demonstrated adaptation and mitigation measures should be framed in the context of climate change to keep in line with the objectives of the project and in particular how one has reduced the impact on climate change of the farm.

Make use of the host farm, and the experience of the host farmer. The opportunity to visit another farm is often one of the main motivations of farmers to attend a demo, so it is important to link the demonstration content to actual farm management conditions on the host farm and provide as many practical examples as possible. This also means paying attention to what has worked well on the farm, ease of implementation or financial gains. There could also be a story or message to an action implemented by a farmer that did not work too well. Ultimately whether it worked very well or wasn't a great success there should be a lesson to be learnt providing information and an insight for all attendees.

5.5.2 | Engage participants in active knowledge exchange

Offer opportunities for peer-to-peer knowledge exchange. You can increase participation in presentations and demonstrations, by e.g. actively giving participants the opportunity to share their experiences with the audience, by organising discussions with smaller numbers of participants, or by organising workshops in which active knowledge exchange is stimulated. Create opportunities for more informal knowledge exchange, by providing enough time for farmers to chat to each other, for example during lunch, drinks, workshops or as farmers move around the farm.

Offer a wide range of experiences and look for ways to surprise participants. Include a range of diverse activities. Examples may be field walks, observing practical demonstrations carried out by a demonstrator, and letting participants carry out hands-on activities. Such practical activities enhance learning and understanding, and also the interactions between participants. By adding a surprise effect to the demonstration activities, participants will more likely remember the information for a longer time. This surprise effect can be generated in different ways, for example, by skillful storytelling techniques, using an original engaging activity for participants, or by revealing a product/innovation during the demo event.

Create a stimulating setting. Events should be setup in such a way that everyone can comfortably listen to and understand the speaker(s) and other participants. Some ideas are:

- Walk the route before hand
- Ensure a planned route is centred around learning outcomes by visiting various parts of farm
- Allow adequate space between the demonstration points, and allow farmers the time to leisurely walk between stops (allows time for conversations and reflections)

- Use microphones so that each participant can hear the speakers (in particular, when outside)
- Use visual material that each participant can see (i.e. do not use posters with small font size, which may be only visible to the front row)
- If indoors: put chairs in a circle/half circle, so everybody has clear sight of the other participants.
- Organise a “market” with different stands/presenters so people can walk around in smaller groups.
- Think about where you will hold discussions, considering that farmers tend to be more at ease in the field or barn, than in scholarly classrooms.
- Provide some funny icebreakers at the beginning of the event. Cracking a joke with the host farmer can often lighten the mood even it means you as the facilitator being the butt of the joke! Attendees immediately feel more comfortable if there is some lighted banter and often tend to share more at events. Even relating to a public or sporting event that was held over the weekend or previous couple of days can break the ice and take the formal setting away from the farm demo event.

5.5.3 | Use a variety of learning methods

Go for a combination. Various learning methods can be employed during demonstration events, e.g. posters, presentations, experiments, discussions, workshops, etc. These methods differ in the degree of interaction between demonstrator and participants and the active engagement required by the farmers, and appeal to different learning styles. Again, the choice of what combination of learning methods is being used depends on the objective of the day, and the group composition and size.

Adapt to different knowledge levels and learning styles in the audience. If possible, get an idea of knowledge levels of your participants in advance. If not, start with basic information for newcomers in the field.

Figure 18: Pie chart outlining different learning styles

Typical types of learners are:

- Auditory learners prefer to hear the information. They often talk to themselves while they are studying or thinking. This can be supported by stimulating the audience to repeat the key messages out loud, e.g. by asking them questions.
- Visual learners prefer to see information and visualize the relationships between ideas, for example in infographics, charts, schemes and colours.
- Reading/writing learners prefer to read or write down information, in booklets or handouts.
- Kinaesthetic (physical) learners prefer to actually perform hands-on exercises and experiments.

Can a combination of learning methods be used?

As a learning activity, demonstrations need to include a variety of learning activities, particularly opportunities for hands-on interaction with the innovation. Activities also need to address a range of learning styles, and require considerable skill to facilitate.

Make use of suitable educational tools- Educational tools are all sorts of materials used during a demo to facilitate learning (e.g. hand-outs, videos, interactive electronic voting systems), to:

- Increase interaction: by, for example, the use of voting systems or interactive apps (e.g., [Mentimeter](#); [Kahoot](#))
- Visualise content: e.g., show equipment used on the farm, posters with engaging infographics (free online infographic makers on [Canva](#)), videos compiled on farm to show 'good' or 'bad' practices.
- Provide supporting information for the demo event: e.g., booklets with additional information on the host farm or a list of attendees. An example of this are the "[farm walk booklets](#)" published by Teagasc
- Provide information to take home: e.g., booklets with practical information on the demonstrated innovation. This is of particular importance, since participants don't always have the opportunity to take notes. Make references to webpage, Instagram, Facebook if available.

Think about how to distribute materials during the demo event. If they are distributed during presentations, it might distract participants. Some of this information can also be sent in advance to the participants if they have pre-registered for the event.

5.6 Examples of exercises to facilitate learning

Exercise	Clover Scorecard (see Figure 13)
Objective of the exercise	To assist farmers to objectively assess the clover content of a paddock/ field, using the visual scorecard.
How it works	Assign farmers to small groups (3 – 5 per group). Provide a scorecard to each group. Select a paddock/ field to be assessed or scored. Starting in one corner, ask the group to walk diagonally across the paddock/ field, visually assessing the clover content on 20 occasions (the group should pause, look at the sward and assign a score at each point). Once the group reaches the far corner, they should review their scores and assign an average score for the overall paddock/ field. All groups should then share their answer with each other to see if there is agreement. The facilitator should have scored the paddock/ field beforehand and should be able to provide the "correct" score.
Resources required	Adequate copies of the clover scorecard

Exercise	Giant Climate Action Jenga (see Figure 14)
Objective of the exercise	To challenge farmers to identify those adaptation and mitigation measures (AMM's) that will have the greatest impact in reducing GHG emissions and that they are most likely to adopt on their farms.
How it works	A group of farmers (5 – 12) are provided with a set of 12 blocks. Each block is labelled with one AMM. Farmers are instructed to construct the Jenga tower starting with the measure with the most impact and most likely to be adopted at ground level, and the measure with the least impact and least likely to be adopted placed at the top of the tower. Farmers are allocated 15 minutes to discuss the AMM's amongst themselves and construct the tower. At the end of the exercise, one farmer from the group is asked to justify their tower design.
Resources	A set of 12 blocks (see Figure 14, each block is 30cm x 10cm x 4 cm (L x W x H) in size) Each block to be labelled with one AMM

Figure 19: An interactive exercise guiding farmers to reduce gaseous emissions on farm (Source: Author's own image)

Figure 18 shows Ireland's Minister for Agriculture, Food and the Marine, Pippa Hackett, completing the 12 Steps Challenge at a recent demonstration event at the Teagasc Tillage Experimental Farm.

During the exercise, a farmer is asked to select those AMM's which they believe that they can implement and will make a difference on their farm from those available on the board on the left, before creating a prioritised list on the second board on the right. In this way, farmers are encouraged to consider the various AMM's and to select those suited to their farm. Many of the AMM's would have been showcased at the event (at other parts of the overall event), so the purpose of this specific part of the event was to move farmers from consideration towards decision and action. Following the selection of the measures, a photo was taken of the completed second board and presented to the farmer.

5.7 Transformative learning

Transformative learning is necessary for substantive whole farm system changes such as reducing GHG emissions. Most farmers prefer to maintain their status quo (or at least remain on the path they have planned), often owing to their economic, social and cultural commitments. Transformative learning entails a shift in a farmer's frame of reference. This ultimately comes about through drawing on previous experience, forcing the farmer into reflection and should be kept in mind when organising on farm demo events over the course of the Climate Farm Demo project. This can be achieved by allowing time for farmers to speak to one another and to think about changes can be implemented on their own farms. One approach to facilitating this is the use of the ORID method (see section 5.8).

Major changes in farming operations often occur in response to major trigger events, such as integrating a successor to the business, financial issues or an outbreak of disease and climate change needs to be seen as in the same frame as the latter for changes to occur on the ground. These trigger events lead to a period of active information seeking. If the innovation appears promising, it is likely to be taken up (at least on a trial basis). The importance of the Triggering Change Model² for on-farm demonstration is that if the demonstration activity promotes major changes, farmers who are dealing with major issues are more likely to take up the innovation or at least attend the event!

Figure 20: The "Triggering change" model redrawn from Sutherland et al.

²Hidano, A., Gates, M.C. and Enticott, G., (2019), Farmers' decision making on livestock trading practices: cowshed culture and behavioral triggers amongst New Zealand dairy farmers. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, Vol. 6, pp.320 - 334.

5.8 ORID method

The ORID (Objective, Reflective, Interpretive, and Decisional) method is a form of a structured conversation led by a facilitator. It is a method that is simple and fast but effective and offers a way to structure conversation and make concrete plans. The method has previously been used in other Farm Demo projects.

Objective – What do I see?

Focus on the facts: what did we see? What was demonstrated?

Reflection – How do I feel?

Reflect on the facts: what did participants like and dislike about what was demonstrated?

Interpretive – What does this mean? For me and others?

Ask the question: so what? What are options, challenges, and opportunities? Are visitors able to implement what was demonstrated in their own context?

Decisional – Now what? What will I do (differently as a result)?

Define concrete actions: what will participants do after the demo?

By answering these questions, more insights are gained into what visitors may still need to implement the climate smart farming practice(s) that were demonstrated, how tacit knowledge can be made explicit, and what needs improvement during a next demo event and what possible follow-up events or activities are necessary.

6. Monitoring, Evaluation and Follow up

Evaluation of a demo event helps to reflect on take-home messages and actions for participants and on areas of improvement for future demo events for the event organisers/ facilitators. Follow-up after the event helps in assessing and understanding whether participants have taken up climate-smart farming practices or are planning to do so. Evaluation and follow-up is focussed on both the short term (what do visitors take home?) as well as on the long term (what do visitors do with what they take home?).

6.1 Monitoring and evaluation methods

Monitoring and evaluation tools help to gather feedback, improve climate-smart demo events and boost the learning experience during a demo. During previous Farm Demo projects, several tools for monitoring and evaluating a demo event have already been developed. They are freely available through the [Farm Demo TrainingKit](#).

Each CFD event **must** be evaluated as it will not count as an event within the project otherwise. The evaluation template will be made available online, while a draft copy is included in the appendix of this guide. Link to website: <https://climatefarmdemo.eu/cfd/#/monitoring-kpis>

6.2 Return to the objective

For any monitoring and evaluation activity, it is important to return to the objectives that were formulated during the planning of the demo event (see Chapter 1). Have we reached the objectives? Are key messages clear to visitors? Returning to the objectives creates space for visitors to reflect on what the demonstration means for them, what actions they can take within their own working context. It also enables demo organisers to improve future demo events, thereby increasing impact of demo events on climate smart farming within the EU.

6.3 Follow-up

Follow-up activities are more focused on the long-term: what do visitors do with what they took home from a demo event? Follow-up activities are important if you want to measure the impact of a demo event. However, they can also be very time consuming. Follow-up tools such as telephone surveys are available in downloadable formats in the [Farm Demo TrainingKit](#).

Less time-consuming follow-up activities include e.g.:

1. Emailing visitors after the event thanking them for their participation and including a summary of lessons learned, possible follow-up actions, and relevant contact information for farmers who want to further inform themselves or take action on what was demonstrated;
2. Reporting on the event in relevant news outlets, social media, etc.;
3. Inviting visitors to next events;
4. Connecting demo events to other ongoing activities such as existing study groups or local/national exchange programmes.

7. Appendices

Appendix 1 Pre-Event Registration Template

GENERAL INFO			
		Enter name of event	
1.	Name of demo event		
		Select from the dropdown menu of predefined answers:	
2.	Agricultural sector	animal husbandry and mixed farming systems	
		specialized arable crops	
		horticulture crops	
		organic farming	
		Select from the dropdown menu all that apply:	
3.	Thematic area	Grassland management	
		Forage production	
		Crops management	
		Soil health and biodiversity	
		Agroforestry and relation to landscape	
		Energy management	
		Biogaz production	
		Water management	
		Herd management	
		Manure storage and spreading	
		Additives for reducing enteric methane emissions	
		Rewarding mechanisms	
Event date		Enter Date	Enter Time
4.	Beginning of event		
5.	End of event		
		Event place	
6.	Where will your event take place?	select from the dropdown menu:	

		Commercial farm (Pilot Demo Farm)
		Experimental farm
		Lighthouse farm
		Online
7.	Name of the farm/organization	
8.	Address of the farm/organization	
9.	Country of the farm/organization	select from the dropdown menu:
		Contact person:
		Contact person email address:
10.	If you need more details, feel free to contact:	
INFO ABOUT THE EVENT:		
		Select one or more of the offered options
11.	Describe the objective of the demo event?	Adoption of innovative CS farming practices
		Farm practice change
		Activation of rewarding mechanisms
		Introduction of the climate smart technology
		Peer to peer knowledge sharing
		Other (please state)
		Select one of the offered options:
12.	Expected number of participants	Between 5 and 20
		Between 20 and 30
		Between 30 and 50
		Between 50 and 100
		More than 100
		Select all that apply:
13.	Target audience	Farmers
		Advisory services
		Research
		Education
		EIP-AGRI Service Point & CAP Network
		Policy makers

		Consumers and citizens
		Media
		Multiple responses possible, please choose all that apply:
14.	How do you promote your activity /event?	Website(s)
		Mailing list
		Social media
		Radio
		TV
		Newsletter
		Farmers Journal
		Leaflets
		Other: please state
15.	Please upload the links and/or documents used for the promotion of events	
Visual representation of the event		
		Upload
16.	Link to event web resource	Please upload picture / logo / event agenda / some other document that would make your event be more visible and appealing

Appendix 2: Suggested Safety Protocol for Climate Farm Demo Events

Safety Protocol for a Climate Farm Demo Event on the farm of _____

This is a Farm Safety Checklist for staff who are organising on farm events. Its main purpose is to:

- a. Ensure the safety of public attending a CFD organised event
- b. Support staff in identifying key safety activities to be undertaken
- c. Have written confirmation on the farm safety activities to be undertaken by staff

Activities Prior to the Event (tick appropriate box, yes or no)

1. Ensure the Pilot Demo Farm is suitable

Advisors should be mindful when selecting pilot demo farms at the outset of the programme as all farms will host three events and it can greatly reduce the problems afterwards. Before the event check the farm again from a safety aspect? Yes No

2. Check Animal Health Status

Did you check with the DVO to ensure that no animal health problems exist on the farm or a major problem on adjoining farm? Yes No

3. Check insurance cover

Did you inform the host farmers insurer and the organisations insurer of the event taking place? Yes No

4. Complete a farm safety plan

Prepare a farm safety plan for the event. It will alert advisors to safety issues they should address when preparing for an event. Also, the plan need only refer to the section of the farm where the event is taking place. Was a safety plan prepared

Yes No

5. Medical backup

Depending on numbers attending, it may be necessary to have trained medics in attendance.

Yes No

6. Signposting

Public signposts should be be suitably placed and clearly visible. These signs should contain the Teagasc logo and be professionally produced (no handwriting). In some cases you may consider informing the local Gardai

Yes No

Activities to be carried out on the day of the event:

1. **Organise Road Signs** Yes No

2. **Organise Parking Arrangements** Yes No

3. **Provide Disinfectant** Yes No

Appendix 3: Suggested Climate Farm Demo Farm Information Template

This template contains a series of headings under which farm details can be entered. CFA's can add, or remove, headings as appropriate. Completion of this template is recommended, but not a project requirement.

Farmer Name and Address

Farm Details

Include details regarding the farm size owned/rented land (ha) and of grassland and cropping areas

Include details regarding the farming system(s)

Organic Status

Livestock Types and Numbers

Include details of the livestock types (dairy cows, suckler cows, 0 – 1 year olds, 1 – 2 year olds, sheep, pigs etc.) – currently on the farm and on average for the previous year

Include farm stocking rate

Include a selection of recent (current, most recent year) performance figures e.g. milk yield, average daily gain, calving pattern, slaughter age etc.

Crop Types

Include details of crops grown (and rotations)

Include a selection of recent (current, most recent year) performance figures e.g. crop yield

People/Management

Include details of people, including other family members, involved in running the farm

Farm Goals

Include short term and long term goals

GHG emissions

Include details of total farm GHG emissions, emissions per hectare farmed and emissions per kg of product produced.

Include details of GHG emissions breakdown (available from Audit)

Other

Include other farm specific details

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Mitigation and adaptation actions

Include details of all mitigation and adaptation actions currently taken on the farm

Include details of planned future mitigation and adaptation actions

*Note: Most of the details required by the CFA to generate this Farm Information Sheet should be available through the initial GHG farm audit and from the AMP generated for each PDF. In many cases, the CFA will be familiar with the farmer and their farm and will be able to complete this fact sheet by having a conversation with the farmer.

Appendix 4: Steps to Promoting a Demo Event

	Person Responsible	Completion Date	Checked
Title for the Advert			
Choose a good name for the demo event that also reflects the key message “Title of the event”			
Inform all stakeholders involved in the event six weeks in advance of the event			
In the advert, include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Catchy title e.g. Turning grass into cash . Clearly define the learning outcome from the event . Location including GPS . Date & time . Use farmer photo . Climate Farm Demo logos . Booking link / QR code 			
Be consistent with the template of advert used			
The Climate Farm Demo logo is to be used on all adverts, local and national as well as partner logo.			
QR to the branded Signpost advert templates.			
Let the PR department know			
Advertising Options			
Letter			
Text messages			
Social media adverts			
Programme website			
Relevant newsletters including enterprise newsletter			
Partners contact lists			
Articles in national papers			
Local radio			
Local paper – adverts			

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Local paper – articles

National adverts

Press release

Event signs

Booking page / booking link

Appendix 5: Evaluation/Post Event Report

This survey is aimed to validate results of the organized demonstration event. Your input from the event is valuable source for the lessons learned and guideline for mapping the points for potential improvements.

This survey refers to both in-person as well as virtual demonstrations.

GENERAL INFO		
1.	Date of event	<i>Select date from calendar</i>
2.	Name of demo event	<i>Enter name of event</i>
3.	Country of demo event	<i>Select from the dropdown menu of predefined answers:</i> List of countries
4.	Total number of participants (from all target groups):	<i>Enter number</i>
<i>Below, please provide a total number of participants per each target group</i>		
5.	Total number of participants per each target group	Farmers
		Farmers organizations
		Advisory services
		Education (Academic and university)
		Research institute
		Consumers and citizens
		Policy makers
		EIP-AGRI Service Point
		CAP networks
		Media
	Other (please state)	
6.	Thematic area	<i>Select from the dropdown menu of predefined answers:</i>

		<i>List of thematic areas</i>
7.	Which Climate Smart Farming practices were demonstrated?	<i>Open field (please state)</i>
8.	Will the proposed solutions be utilized on the participants' farms? (Based on interaction with attendees)	<i>Open field (please state)</i>
9.	What didn't work well at the event - observation (Based on interaction with attendees)	<i>Open field (please state)</i>
10.	Participants' suggestions- how to improve the demo event (Based on interaction with attendees)	<i>Open field (please state)</i>
<i>Please, describe in English language (max 150 characters)</i>		
11.	Event implementation (how, what was presented, structure of demonstration)	
<i>Please, describe in local language (max 150 characters)</i>		
12.	Event implementation (how, what was presented, structure of demonstration)	
<i>Below please describe in max 200 characters</i>		
13.	Please describe rate your overall satisfaction with event delivery	
14.	What would you do differently if organizing a similar event in the future?	
Visual representation of the event		
		<i>Please upload picture / logo / event agenda / some other document related to the event</i>

15.	Documents related to event	<i>File 1</i>
		<i>File 2</i>
		<i>File 3</i>
		<i>File 4</i>
16.	Link to event web resource	
17.	Participant and/or organizer testimonial	Link to event web resource (optional)

Appendix 6: Frequently Asked Questions

1. How many demonstrations per year?

Answer: Each farmer should host three demo events over six years period, or a demonstration every second year. The total number of demonstrations per partner or per country will then depend on the number of farmers being supported. It would be a good idea to link demos to the application of the AMP. The first demo event (Year 1 or 2) could focus on presentation of the farm and the AMP. The second event could focus on the progress (Year 3 or 4), while the third event could present the result of the final audit (and hopefully report progress in reducing GHG emissions). This would show evolution on the farm.

2. What do you mean with CFA is to deliver the demo event?

Answer: The CFA is the person responsible for the planning, organisation, delivery and evaluation of each demo event. This doesn't mean that they have to do everything personally, but they have to ensure that the event is facilitated according to the Climate Farm Demo Event Guidelines (WP3). It is acceptable if the CFA works with a colleague to deliver the event.

3. Do the events have to take physically place on the farm or could they just take place with a given farmer (and other farmers)?

Answer: Yes, the project preference is for the events to be face-to-face, on the demonstration farm. This is because part of the reason for the success of demo events is the opportunity provided for other farmers to see, touch, smell, experience the technology on a real farm.

4. Will 'Lighthouse Farm' host demonstrations?

Answer: Lighthouse farms are also demo farms that will host demonstrations. In addition, there will be a separate network and support developed for the lighthouse farms. This is still under development and will be ready by the annual meeting in October.

5. What do we mean by “adaptation”?

Answer: Adaptation is the process whereby farmers adapt taking on the right measures to reduce the negative effects of climate change.

6. What are adaptation actions?

Answer: Adaptation actions aim to reduce the impacts of climate change but to also take advantage of any opportunities presented by climate change.

7. What do we mean by “mitigation”?

Answer: Mitigation is a human intervention to reduce the sources or enhance the sinks of greenhouse gases.

8. What are mitigation actions?

Answer: Mitigation actions focus on limiting the rate and scale of future climate change by reducing levels of greenhouse gas emissions and increasing GHG sinks. Integration of mitigation and adaptation In the agriculture, forest and seafood sector, adaptation and mitigation are more integrated than in other sectors, therefore these actions can and should work in an integrated manner to maximise co-benefits and to decrease the impacts of climate change on rural and coastal livelihoods and enhance the resilience of our food, fibre and fuel production systems.

9. How should I announce and report my demo events?

Answer: All events must be registered on the CFD project website (<https://climatefarmdemo.eu/>) and evaluated after the event also. An advisor is free to advertise the event anywhere provided it is registered on the project’s official website.

10. How many participants can attend an event?

Answer: There is no limit on the number of participants who can attend an event but advisors must be mindful to have adequate facilities, parking, toilet facilities etc... in place to cater for greater numbers.

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